

KINETICS OF THE FORMATION OF ANILIDES. PART I.

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The reaction between methyl esters of substituted benzoic acids and aniline has been studied with nitrobenzene and xylene as solvents. The reaction has been shown to be bimolecular and the activation energy, E and the probability factor, P have been calculated in each case. A mechanism, parallel to alkaline hydrolysis of esters, has been proposed and the effect of the substituents has been explained on the basis of this mechanism. A relationship is shown between the reaction velocity and the dipole moments of substituted benzenes.

The reaction of esters with aniline or other primary amines does not appear to have been studied in detail so far. Menshutkin (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1906, I, 551) studied the kinetics of the reaction of aliphatic acids with the excess of aniline, toluidines or xylydines. The reaction was confined to aliphatic acids. The reaction is catalysed by halogen acids or their ammonium salts.

Goldschmidt (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 97) studied the velocity of reaction between aliphatic acids, aniline and toluidine and showed the reaction to be bimolecular. In the presence of picric acid as a catalyst, the reaction was of the first order and the temperature coefficient was about 2 as in the case of the catalysed reactions.

Davies (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1911, 78, 353) studied the rate of hydrolysis of anilides by sodium hydroxide with a view to ascertaining the effect of substituents on the rate of the reaction and these observed rates were compared with the equilibrium constant of the formation of anilides from the acid and an aromatic base. A parallelism between the two was shown. McBain and Davies (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1911, 78, 369) have compared the equilibrium constants of the anilides with the dissociation constants of acids and amines. There is also a parallelism between these constants and the effect of the substituents on them.

Audrieth and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 579; 1939, 61, 2387; 1940, 63, 2965) studied the reaction between esters and aliphatic amines in order to ascertain the mechanism of the reaction. They have suggested that the 'onium' ion is the active catalyst.

Betts and Hammett (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 1568) studied the rates of reaction of phenylacetic esters with ammonia in methyl alcohol at 25° and showed that the two reactions occurred simultaneously, one uncatalysed reaction of ester with ammonia and a parallel base-catalysed reaction of ester with the amide ion.

The present communication deals with the kinetics of the reaction between aniline and methyl esters of twenty substituted benzoic acids,

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Aniline was dried over solid potassium hydroxide and fractionally distilled. Nitrobenzene was shaken with calcium carbonate and dried over calcium chloride. It was then distilled under reduced pressure. Xylene was dried over sodium and then over phosphorus pentoxide and distilled. All the esters were prepared by standard methods and purified after drying by fractional distillation. Top and bottom fractions were rejected and fractions boiling within less than one degree used for the experiments. The boiling points and other constants agreed closely with those reported in the literature. The solvents used were nitrobenzene and xylene.

The velocity constants were determined at four or more temperatures between 80° and 145° in a thermostat. The temperatures used were very much lower than the boiling points of the esters. The reaction was carried out in hard glass test-tubes in which a known volume of the reaction mixture of the requisite concentration was introduced.

Method of Analysis.—The test-tubes were removed from the thermostat, chilled and analysed according to the following procedure: (a) At the end of a certain period, a test-tube containing a reaction mixture of the base, the ester and the anilide in the solvent was taken out and chilled. (b) The well cooled mixture was then washed with a total quantity of 50 c. c. of 4% hydrochloric acid in four equal lots and the base was thus extracted from the reaction mixture in the washings. (c) The washings were collected and made up to a fixed volume (100 c. c.). A known volume of the washings was then analysed by the bromate-bromide method and the base estimated.

The method of analysis described above was checked by preparing synthetic mixture of the reaction products of similar concentration in nitrobenzene, xylene and chlorobenzene. The estimated quantity of the base agreed within 1% with the quantity actually taken.

Nature of the Reaction.—The reaction of a base and an ester can be represented as

The experiments were conducted to determine whether there was an equilibrium attained in the course of the reaction. When a reaction mixture containing methyl benzoate and aniline (both 0.1 g. mol./litre) in nitrobenzene was heated at 100° for 170 hours, the anilide formation occurred to the extent of about 97%. The reverse reaction was studied by heating at 100° for several hours a mixture of the anilide and methyl alcohol of the same concentration and in the same solvent in a closed system. The analysis of the mixture after 170 hours showed that the reverse reaction did not occur at all. It is concluded therefore that the reaction goes to completion and the reverse reaction is not appreciable.

*N*⁴-*Sulphanilamido- α -propionic Ester* (III).—Sulphanilamide (7 g.) and α -bromoethyl propionate (5 g.) were reacted together and a product obtained as in (I). It was crystallised from dilute alcohol as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 110°, yield 4 g. (Found: N, 10.51. $C_{11}H_{13}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 10.3 per cent).

*N*⁴-*Sulphanilamido- α -propionic Acid* (IV).—*N*⁴-sulphanilamido- α -propionic ester (2.7 g.) and potassium hydroxide (1.5 g.) in water (20 c.c.) were refluxed together for 6 hours. The solution was concentrated to a smaller volume (nearly 7 c.c.) and worked up as under (II). The product was obtained as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 180-81°, yield 2 g. (Found: N, 11.12. $C_9H_{11}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 11.47 per cent).

*N*⁴-*Sulphanilamido- α -butyric Ester* (V).—Sulphanilamide (10 g.) and ethyl α -bromobutyrate (6 g.) in absolute alcohol (50 c. c.) were refluxed for 24 hours. The product was isolated and purified as under (I) as a white amorphous product, m. p. 117°, yield 4.5 g. (Found: N, 10.18; S, 11.6. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 9.79; S, 11.14 per cent).

*N*⁴-*Sulphanilamido- α -butyric Acid* (VI).—*N*⁴-Sulphanilamido- α -butyric ester (3 g.) was hydrolysed and the product obtained in exactly the same manner as in (II) as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 172°, yield 2.7 g. (Found: N, 10.8. $C_{10}H_{12}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 10.25 per cent).

*N*⁴-*Sulphanilamidodiethyl Malonate* (VII).—Sulphanilamide (7 g.) and ethyl bromomalonate (5 g.) in absolute alcohol (20 c. c.) were refluxed together for 15 hours. The product was isolated and crystallised as described in (I) as a white crystalline powder, m. p. 171-72°, yield 4.5 g. (Found: N, 8.42. $C_{13}H_{15}O_6N_2S$ requires N, 8.5 per cent).

*N*⁴-*Sulphanilamidomalonic Acid* (VIII).—*N*⁴-Sulphanilamidodiethyl malonate (2.3 g.) was hydrolysed as under (IV). The product was obtained as a white powder after crystallisation from water, m. p. 236° (decomp.), yield 2 g. (Found: N, 10.3. $C_9H_{10}O_6N_2S$ requires N, 10.21 per cent).

Sulphanilamidophenylacetic Ester (IX).—Sulphanilamide (7 g.) ethyl bromophenylacetate (5 g.) in absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) were refluxed together for 15 hours. The alcohol was distilled off and the residue was stirred with benzene (15 c.c.). The product was filtered and washed with ether, and worked up as described in (I). Finally crystallised from dilute alcohol it was obtained as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 126°, yield 6 g. (Found: N, 8.58; S, 9.4. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 8.38; S, 9.58 per cent).

*N*⁴-*Sulphanilamidophenylacetic Acid* (X).—*N*⁴-Sulphanilamidophenylacetic ester (3.3 g.) was saponified as in (II). In this case, the product was crystallised from dilute alcohol as a white powder, m. p. 189° (decomp.), yield 2 g. (Found: N, 8.8. $C_{13}H_{14}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 9.15 per cent).